

Palercha and Gour⁴ have also polarographically studied aspirin complexes with cadmium, lead and copper, and reported 1:1 and 1:2 complexes for both lead and cadmium, and for copper 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes. The present work has been undertaken with a view to establish the composition and to determine the formation constant of the aspirinato complex by using Kolthoff and Lingane⁵ equations.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of Analar quality Sodium molybdate which on analysis was found to have the formula $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Gelatin (0.01%) was used as a maximum suppressor and purified hydrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. Doubly distilled mercury was used for DME.

Polarograms were obtained in the conventional manner using a recording type polarograph "PO₄ Radiometer Polariter". Measurement of pH was done on a Beckmann pH meter, using a combined glass calomel electrode. The drop time, sensitivity, damping and chart speed were kept constant throughout the operation. All the operations were carried out at room temperature.

A series of polarograms were obtained with different concentrations of the ligand. These exhibit a shift in the half wave potential of molybdenum (VI) towards a positive direction with increasing concentrations of the ligand. The changes in the $E_{1/2}$ when plotted against the logarithm of the corresponding ligand concentrations give a straight line, the slope of which gives the ratio of change in half wave potential and change in ligand concentration. This ratio has been used in the calculation of the formation constant⁶.

The reversibility of the electrode reaction was verified by plotting $\log_{10} \frac{(I_d - I)}{I}$ against the corresponding potential E , where I_d and I are the diffusion current and current at the applied potential E respectively.

In forming 1:2 complex two aspirinate anions replace two of the four coordinated oxygen atoms around the molybdenum (VI) atom in a tetrahedral structure. The formation constant of the complex is found to be 2.92×10^{-5} .

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Some New Uses of Ferroin as Redox Indicator

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THE use of ferroin as redox indicator in the dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II) and hydroquinone and the vanadometric titration of hydroquinone has not been reported till now. We have now been able to develop conditions under which this can be achieved and the results are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. quality.

The following procedures are recommended for the titrations.

Dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II).

Treat an aliquot of 0.1 *N* hexacyanoferrate (II) solution with enough 1:1 sulphuric acid, to give an overall acidity of 2-4 *M*, and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute the mixture to 50 ml (or 100 ml if the amount of hexacyanoferrate (II) exceeds 4 moles) and titrate with 0.1 *N* potassium dichromate solution till the colour sharply changes from orange yellow to yellowish green.

Dichrometric titration of hydroquinone :

Treat an aliquot of hydroquinone solution (0.1 *N*) with the requisite amount of 1:1 sulphuric acid, such that the overall acidity is 2-4 *M*, 0.5 ml of 1% hexacyanoferrate (IV) or 5-10 ml of 0.1 *N* uranium (VI) or 20 ml of 0.1 *N* iron (III) and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* potassium dichromate solution. The colour change at the end point is from orange red to yellowish green.

Vanadometric titration of hydroquinone :

To the sample solution, containing 0.1 to 0.4 moles of hydroquinone, add enough sulphuric acid (1:1) to give an overall acidity of 5-6 *M*, 2.5-5.0 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* sodium vanadate solution till the colour changes sharply from orange red to blue.

Results and Discussion

Dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II).

This titration can also be performed in media of 3-5 *M* hydrochloric acid and 4-6 *M* phosphoric acid. The same procedure can be followed in titrations involving 0.01 *N* hexacyanoferrate (II) with 0.01 *N* potassium dichromate provided an indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01 *N* dichromate is applied.

The reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of dichromate with hexacyanoferrate (II), using ferroin as indicator, also are possible under the same conditions of direct titration. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the method now developed for the reverse titration is advantageous over that reported [by Someya¹ who prescribes a potentiometric titration at elevated temperatures (40°-50°)].

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Our experiments have shown that the oxidation of ferroin by dichromate occurs instantaneously only in a medium which is at least 5 *M* in sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid or 7 *M* in phosphoric acid, whereas the titration of hexacyanoferrate(II) is possible even at lower acidities. A detailed investigation of this anomaly has shown that at lower acidities, the ferroin-dichromate reaction is (1) induced by hexacyanoferrate(II), (2) catalysed by hexacyanoferrate(III), and (3) unaffected by chromium(III). Thus this is a case of induction and autocatalysis. Separate experiments have shown that the reduction of ferroin by hexacyanoferrate(II) is almost instantaneous under the conditions of titration.

Dichrometric titration of hydroquinone: The titration of hydroquinone with potassium dichromate using ferroin as indicator can also be carried out in 2-4 *M* hydrochloric acid or 4.5-7.0 *M* phosphoric acid medium, if the titration mixture contains 0.5 ml of 1% potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) or 5-10 ml of 0.1*N* uranium(VI). The titration is also possible in a medium of 8-10*M* phosphoric acid, provided it is carried out slowly in the vicinity of the end point, waiting for about 10-15 sec. after each addition.

Titration of 0.01 *N* solutions of hydroquinone with 0.01 *N* dichromate solution are also satisfactory; in this case, an indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01 *N* dichromate has to be applied.

The titrations of dichromate with hydroquinone also can be carried out under the same conditions of direct titrations. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the procedure now developed by the authors is advantageous over those reported by Kolthoff² (potentiometric titration) and Simon and Zyka³ (40°-50° and diphenylamine as indicator).

The possibility of the titration of hydroquinone with dichromate at lower acid concentrations and the role of hexacyanoferrate(III), uranium (VI) and iron(III) in this titration are similar to those recently reported by us in the dichrometric titration of hydroquinone using triphenylmethane dyes as redox indicators⁴.

Vanadometric titration of hydroquinone: The vanadometric titration of hydroquinone, employing ferroin as indicator, gives very good results when carried out in 7-10 *M* phosphoric acid medium also, whereas in hydrochloric acid medium, the end points are fleeting and the colour change at the end point is not at all satisfactory.

The reverse titration, i. e., titration of vanadate with hydroquinone employing ferroin as indicator, can be performed under the same conditions of the direct titration and is advantageous over those of Kolthoff² and Simon and Zyka³.

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Fluoroniobates (V) of Organic Base Cations

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A large number of fluoroniobates of various metals are known¹⁻³. Recently a series of compounds containing protonated hydrazine and ethylenediamine have been reported by Buslaev and others⁴. The present work deals with the isolation of fluoroniobates of various other organic base cations.

Experimental

Methods of Analysis: The compounds were decomposed by (1 : 1) H₂SO₄ and niobium was then gravimetrically estimated as niobium pentoxide from its cupferronate precipitate. Fluorine was estimated gravimetrically as lead chlorofluoride after separating niobium as hydrated niobium pentoxide. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method.

The analytical results are reported in Table I.

1. Oxotetrafluoroniobates, BH(NbOF₄), where B = Pyridine, α -, β -, δ -picolines and quinoline : Nb₂O₅ was dissolved in minimum volume of 40% hydrofluoric acid by heating on a water bath. Calculated amount of organic base (Nb₂O₅ : organic base = 1 : 2) was acidified with 10% HF and then added dropwise to the above solution. The resulting mixture was evaporated on a water bath to crystallisation. The crystals were filtered, pressed between filter papers and dried to constant weight in vacuum over H₂SO₄ and KOH.

2. Guanidinium oxopentafluoroniobate, CH₅N₃H₂(NbOF₅) : The compound was prepared through the above procedure from Nb₂O₅ and guanidine carbonate in 2 : 1 ratio.

3. *o*-phenanthroline oxotetrafluoroniobate, C₁₂H₈N₂H(NbOF₄) : By the above procedure the compound was obtained as a white crystalline precipitate on mixing the two components in the cold condition in 1 : 1 ratio.

4. Nitron hexafluoroniobate, C₂₀H₁₆N₄H(NbF₆) : Dark brown crystals of the compound was obtained on dropwise addition of glacial acetic acid solution of nitron (Nb₂O₅ : Nitron = 1 : 1) to a hot solution of fluoroniobate prepared as before. The resulting mixture was partially evaporated on a water bath and the crystals obtained were filtered and dried as above.

5. α , α' -dipyridyl hexafluoroniobate, C₁₀H₈N₂H₂(NbF₆)₂ : The compound was prepared as the above oxotetrafluoroniobates from Nb₂O₅ : α , α' -dipyridyl in 1 : 1 ratio.